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**“The Competency of Teachers to Facilitate Diversified Learners in the Public
School Practicing Inclusive Education Program”**

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Abstract: *The policies and acts shown a clear direction to the international and national organizations to practice and facilitate as close as possible within the existing educational program. This direction also recommended for reasonable accommodation by providing necessary teaching and learning experiences to the children with diverse learners including special need children. The purpose of study is to understand the capabilities of teachers to facilitate various learners in inclusive education settings. To identify the basic skills and methods needed for understanding the children with special needs, transferring their skill of teaching and to considering the effects of teacher competence on the didactic and other activities of students concern in inclusive classrooms is focused in this study.*

This study involves a qualitative method using the stratified sampling technique with six hundred teachers working in government schools of various levels. The result shows that there is strong organizational and counseling skills enhance teachers' effectiveness in supporting students with disabilities. Teachers with positive skills were better in facilitating the needs of students with diverse learning. The challenges included inadequate resources and a lack of specialized training in different areas.

It was found that the overall abilities of teachers to accommodate diverse learner is a notable activity for the success of inclusive education programs. The impact of effective strategies, skills, and resources on students' academic performance, social integration, and emotional well-being is the basis for further professional development and support in inclusive classrooms.

Keywords: *Teacher Competency, Inclusive Education, Diversity in Education, Disabilities, Teaching Strategies.*

INTRODUCTION:

Much like others, the special educational landscape in certain district of Tamil Nadu faces challenges when it comes to meeting different student needs, especially in special and inclusive schools (Haldar et al., 2024) (Gopalakrishnan, 2023). Such schools aim to offer equal educational opportunities for children with different disabilities such as blindness, deafness, intellectual and developmental impairments, and locomotor impairments (Parveen, 2022)(Urban & Bucșă, 2023). Teacher competency is essential to achieving this objective (Qobilovna, 2023). It is essential to understand and evaluate the competencies needed for effective teaching in such contexts to ensure that all students receive the support they need to succeed (Purwanto, 2022).

To evaluate teacher competence, quantitative and qualitative research methods are often employed (Santagata et al., 2021) (Proudfoot, 2023). Surveys and questionnaires are used to gather information about different competencies, including organizational skills, teaching techniques, and counseling abilities. These tools assess instructors' performance in delivering differentiated education and support to children with special needs (Martzoukou et al., 2022). Observational approaches and interviews with teachers and administrators can, therefore, provide more information on how these competencies are applied in the classroom (Rogers, 2021).

The benefits of assessing teacher competency include detecting strengths and weaknesses, which may shape targeted professional development and improve student outcomes in the educational process for students with disabilities (Sims & Fletcher-Wood, 2021)(Irasuti& Bachtiar, 2024). Evaluation of this nature ensures teaching methods are aligned with the best practices and educational standards of inclusive

education (Kurth et al., 2020)(Dignath et al., 2022). However, there are several limitations, including potential biases in self-reported data and the difficulty of explicitly quantifying the impact of teacher competence on student results. In addition, implementing evaluation results may require additional resources and structural changes (Lauermann & ten Hagen, 2021).

Recent studies have discussed many dimensions of teachers' competencies and readiness to support students with disabilities in mainstream classrooms. Anne and Rashid (2024) focused on special education teachers' knowledge, skills, and awareness of supporting students with disabilities. The survey they conducted among 80 instructors revealed that there is a diversified teacher community who mainly acknowledge the variety of students' skills and are efficient in communication. Yet only 40% felt secure in using technology in the classroom, and the study underlined the interdependence of several competencies, such as teaching knowledge and psychosocial support. Analogously, Adams et al. (2023) have explored teacher preparation for inclusive education, highlighting the role of self-assessment and the characteristics that affect the competence of teachers in teaching pupils with special needs, for instance, training, gender, and experience as a teacher.

In addition to the competencies of teachers, several studies have focused on the factors that contribute to the success of teachers in an inclusive classroom. Deniz & Ilik (2021) and Koliqi & Zabeli (2022) examined the professional competencies of teachers in the context of inclusive education and found that instructors need more structured support to enhance their skills and self-confidence.

Continue to the above studies Lis Haerunisa et al (2026) observed that the integrated training model with school action research was effective in improving the teacher's competency and to help their professional development with sustainability. Dipak Bhattacharya (2025) found a significant gap in the digital education and skill on technology with the teachers and suggested for training on the technological skill. Alsolami (2022) investigated the use of assistive technology by special education teachers, and the results were that they possessed a moderate level of skill and had a high demand for further training. Alnahdi and Schwab (2021) found that teachers'

attitudes toward inclusive education played a significant role in determining their self-efficacy, showing the importance of good attitudes for effective inclusion. Yılmaz et al. (2021) outlined the ICT skills requirement for special education teachers in COVID-19. These studies, among those of Kuyini et al. (2020), Ogba et al. (2020), and Sowiyah& Zulaikha Fitriyanti (2022), point towards the preparation and support required by teachers to implement the policy of inclusive education efficiently. These findings help to understand the nature of teacher abilities with individual differences in inclusive education and offer significant insights for enhancing teacher training and support systems in various areas and educational contexts.

The purpose of this research is to assess the abilities of teachers in working for inclusive education program in public school of Tamil Nadu. The purpose of the study is to offer practical insights into educational practices and support systems by evaluating their skills in organizational ability, teaching methods for diverse disabilities, and counseling. The findings will be used to develop more effective training programs, enhance teaching practices, and ultimately improve educational experiences and outcomes for children with special needs in the region. The main objectives of the study are

- To assess the level of organizational competency among teachers in special and inclusive schools within the Cauvery Delta Region.
- To evaluate the effectiveness of teaching strategies employed by teachers for children with various disabilities.
- To analyze the counselling competencies of teachers and their impact on supporting the emotional and psychological needs of students with special needs.

METHODS:

Methodology:

The current study focused on a well-defined issue with specific objectives and uses a survey methodology to gather data from concern field. The study was aimed to collect the data from the government school teachers who closely worked with children with disabilities in inclusive setup as per the Govt Scheme practices. The data was collected using a teacher's competency checklist through interview and observational method. An informed consent was obtained prior to the data collection to participate in the study (Ethical practice). The teacher who willingly agreed to participate in the study was included. All the teachers who worked with at least one child in one class during their working experience were included in the study. The teachers who had no idea about children with disability were excluded from the study.

A priori sample size of 500 was estimated using G power for a power of 95% and an effect size of 0.5. However, purposive sample of 300 government primary, middle, high, and upper secondary schools teachers in a region of Tamil Nadu were part of the study. The data included 600 respondents after filtering out the exclusion criteria (50) and attrition (215).

Instrument and validity of the tool:

The Teachers Competency Checklist Supporting Learners with Diversity was developed and validates with the subject experts. The checklist is a 4 point likert rating scale consisting of 26 sub groups under 10 categories. (Appendix II) Hence this Teachers' Competency Checklist, had a coefficient of 0.932. To ensure that the tool adequately measures teachers' skills to support different learners, validity was established both in terms of face and content validity.

Procedure for data collection:

After obtaining permission from the concern department, the interviewer contacted the schools and obtains the data from the teachers by using the checklist

with the identified protocol. The data collection was done only after the Institutional review board clearance.

The obtained data was subjected to descriptive (mean and standard deviation) and inferential statistical, including ANOVA, factor analysis, regression analysis, and Pearson correlation techniques are used to analyze the data of this study using IBM SPSS v. 26.0.

Results:

The obtained data had the following demographic parameters, Gender, Age in Years, Education Status, Marital Status, Total Years of Service, Total Years of Service to Education of Children with Special Needs, School Level, and Location

Table 1: Showing the data of demographic variables

Variables	Data in percentage	Data in percentage	Data in percentage
Gender	49.3 (Male)	50.7 (Female)	0
Age	44.2 (Below 30)	41.3 (30 -40)	14.5 (Above 40)
Education	16.8 (UG+BEd)	83.2 PG+BEd)	0
Marital status	73.3 (Married)	26.7 (Unmarried)	0
Experience	12 (Below 10)	57.3 (10-20)	30.7 (20 Above)
Experience on CWSN	41.5 (Below 10)	49.5 (10 – 20)	9.0 (20 Above)
Location	22.2 (Village)	77.8 (Taluk& Dist)	0
Level of School	32.5 (Primary)	32.5 (Middle)	35 (High& Hr Sec)

Figure 1 : Showing the demographic variables

4.2 Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive statistics shows the important variables for 600 respondents. The gender mean of 1.51 suggests a roughly equal number of male and female responders. Age in years (mean = 1.70, SD = 0.707) indicates that the majority of responses fall into a given age category. The community (mean = 2.21, SD = 0.721) displays the diversity of its participants. Education status (mean = 1.83, SD = 0.374) reveals that the majority have higher education qualifications, while 21% have special education training certificates. The majority of respondents have more than two years of experience in education (mean = 2.19, SD = 0.626), with slightly less time in special needs education (mean = 1.68, SD = 0.632). The school level (mean = 2.03, SD = 0.822) and location (mean = 1.78, SD = 0.416) indicate different educational contexts.

Scores for occupational competency tests (OCT) and disability-specific areas (VI, HI, IDD, etc.) have comparatively high means (3.67-3.96), showing significant competencies among individuals.

4.3 T-Test

The t-test ascertains if the means of the provided variables are substantially different from a test value of zero. All variables have very significant results ($p < 0.001$), meaning their means are significantly higher than zero. Gender ($t = 73.756$), Age in Years ($t = 59.035$), and Community ($t = 74.863$) all have significant positive MD, showing respondent variety. Educational qualifications are very significant ($t = 119.812$), with a mean difference of 1.832. Experience indicators, such as Total Years of Service ($t = 85.497$) and Years of Service in Special Needs Education ($t = 64.869$), demonstrate significant tenure in the education area. Training-related variables such as Training Certificates ($t = 73.053$) and Vocational Training ($t = 73.956$) show significant positive MD. Competency scores (OCT, VI, HI, etc.) have extremely high t-values (>100), showing significant disability-specific abilities. These findings show the respondents' qualifications and competencies in their respective roles.

Table 3: ANOVA

		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig	
Between People		7457.761	599	12.450			
Within People	Between Items	810.803	52	15.592	17.564	.000	
	Residual	Non-additivity	18.537 ^a	1	18.537	20.894	.000
		Balance	27632.736	31147	.887		
		Total	27651.272	31148	.888		
	Total	28462.075	31200	.912			
Total		35919.836	31799	1.130			

4.4 ANOVA

ANOVA Table 3 investigates variation across and within groups. The Between People Sum of Squares (SS = 7457.761, df = 599) shows individual differences among the 600 respondents, with a mean square (MS) of 12.450. Within People variance, the Between Items SS = 810.803 (df = 52) represents variability across items, with a high F-value (17.564, $p < 0.001$) indicating significant differences. The Residual SS (Balance = 27632.736, df = 31147) adjusts for unstructured variability and has a low mean square of 0.887, indicating little unexplained variation. Non-additivity (SS = 18.537, $F = 20.894$, $p < 0.001$) reveals systematic patterns missed by additive models. The total variance (SS = 35919.836, df = 31799) confirms the dataset's complexity, with a mean square of 1.130. As a result, significant results across categories indicate significant diversity between respondents and items, demonstrating the data's robustness and the factors' explanatory value.

4.5 Hotelling's T-Squared

Table 4 shows the results of Hotelling's T-squared test, which is used to compare mean vectors from two groups. The T-squared statistic of 622.323 indicates a significant difference between the groups being compared. The F-value is 10.949, with degrees of freedom (df1 = 52, df2 = 548). The significance value (Sig.) is 0.000, which is less than the standard alpha level of 0.05, indicating that the difference between groups is statistically significant.

Table 4:Hotelling's T-Squared

Hotelling's T-Squared	F	df1	df2	Sig
622.323	10.949	52	548	.000

4.6 Correlation

Table 5:Correlation

	OCT	VI	HI	IDD	LI	MD	CC
OCT	1.000	.840	.513	.550	.583	.557	.598
VI	.840	1.000	.593	.562	.572	.576	.586
HI	.513	.593	1.000	.585	.752	.543	.606
IDD	.550	.562	.585	1.000	.585	.859	.737
LI	.583	.572	.752	.585	1.000	.537	.487
MD	.557	.576	.543	.859	.537	1.000	.778
CC	.598	.586	.606	.737	.487	.778	1.000

Table 5 . The findings show a strong positive correlation (0.840) between OCT and VI, implying that stronger organizational competency is directly related to improved education for children with visual impairments. OCT also has moderate to high positive relationships with HI (0.513), IDD (0.550), LI (0.583), MD (0.557), and CC (0.598), implying that organizational competency correlates with teaching competency for a variety of disabilities. VI is substantially correlated with HI (0.593), IDD (0.562), and CC (0.586), whereas HI has a strong link with LI (0.752) and MD (0.543). IDD had the strongest correlation with MD (0.859), indicating a strong relationship. These findings imply that organizational and teaching qualities across impairments are linked.

4.7 Regression Analysis

Table 6: Regression Analysis

	R	R Square	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
VI	.840 ^a	.706	287.045	1	287.045	1435.019	.000 ^b
HI	.606 ^a	.367	154.484	1	154.484	347.265	.000 ^b
LI	.587 ^a	.337	135.641	1	135.641	310.701	.000 ^b
IDD	.550 ^a	.363	151.482	1	151.482	341.977	.000 ^b

Table 6 shows the model for VI reveals a good correlation ($R = 0.840$) with an R-squared value of 0.706, indicating that VI accounts for 70.6% of the variation in the dependent variable. The F-value of 1435.019 and p-value of 0.000 shows that the model is extremely significant. HI has a moderate correlation ($R = 0.606$) and an R-squared of 0.367, indicating that the model explains 36.7% of the variation. The F-value of 347.265, with a significance level of 0.000, validates the model's importance. The R-value for LI is 0.587, and the R-squared value of 0.337 implies that 33.7% of the variation can be explained. The F-value of 310.701 and p-value of 0.000 indicate statistical significance. For IDD, the R-squared value of 0.363 indicates that 36.3% of the variation is explained, with an F-value of 341.977 and a p-value of 0.000. All models have statistical significance.

5 Analysis:

The analytical results demonstrate that Hypothesis 1 is supported, with a high positive association between organizational competency (OCT) and instructional competency for children with visual impairment (VI). The correlation coefficient of 0.840, as well as the regression analysis results, including an R-squared value of 0.706, show that organizational competency accounts for 70.6% of the variation in teaching competency for children with visual impairment. This link is extremely statistically significant, with an F-value of 1435.019 and a p-value of 0.000.

Hypothesis 2 is similarly accepted, as there is a moderate positive relationship between counseling competency (CC) and teaching competency for children with hearing impairment (HI). The correlation coefficient of 0.606 indicates a significant association, and the regression model yields an R-squared value of 0.367, indicating that counselling competency explains 36.7% of the variance in teaching competency for hearing impairment. The F-value of 347.265 and p-value of 0.000 indicate that this model is statistically significant.

The study for Hypothesis 3 shows a moderate positive connection ($r=0.550$) between organizational competency (OCT) and instructional competency for children with intellectual and developmental disabilities (IDD). According to the R-squared value of 0.363, organizational competency accounts for 36.3% of the variance in IDD teaching competency. The model's statistical significance is validated with an F-value of 341.977 and a p-value of 0.000, indicating that this hypothesis is accepted.

Lastly, Hypothesis 4 is accepted since there is a moderate positive relationship between counselling competency and teaching competency for children with locomotor impairment. This is indicated by the coefficient of 0.487, meaning the relationship is moderate in strength. The regression revealed that R-squared was at 0.337. This implies that counselling competency explains 33.7% of the variation of teaching competency for children with locomotor impairment. The connection is statistically significant, where the F-value is 310.701 and the p-value is 0.000.

Discussion:

As Qobilovna (2023) pointed out that the teacher competency is essential to achieving the objectives of implementing inclusive education this study also advocates on building teachers competency to understand and support in providing education to the diversified learners in their class room implementing inclusive education. Purwanto (2022) also felt in the similar way of understanding and evaluating the teachers competency for extending maximum support and effective interaction with the learners of diversity in the class room To evaluate teacher competence, quantitative and qualitative research methods are often employed (Santagata et al., 2021) (Proudfoot, 2023). Surveys and questionnaires are used to gather information about different competencies, including organizational skills, teaching techniques, and counseling abilities. These tools assess instructors' performance in delivering differentiated education and support to children with special needs (Martzoukou et al., 2022). Observational approaches and interviews with teachers and administrators can, therefore, provide more information on how these competencies are applied in the classroom (Rogers, 2021).

5 Conclusion

The study has given emphasis to the crucial role of teachers in inclusive education programs, especially concerning diverse learning needs. It shows that the effectiveness of teaching tactics, organizational competency, and emotional and psychological support of teachers enhance students' academic performance, social integration, and emotional well-being. It is found that continuous professional development, access to adequate resources, and skill up-gradation are essential in establishing an inclusive learning environment. This particular objective was to study teachers' organizational competency in special and inclusive schools across the region of Tamil Nadu. Results show the need for an integrated strategy for inclusive education through developing skills, availability of resources, and strategic approaches in teaching. This requires individualized training programs and institutional support to ensure instructors are capable of attending to the needs of their students and thus providing a fair and inclusive education system.

6 Implications

The study of teachers' skills in assisting diverse learners in inclusive education programs has important implications for education policy, teacher training, and classroom practice. It emphasizes the importance of continual professional development to provide teachers with the skills and tactics they need to effectively handle the different needs of their students. Specialized training in inclusive teaching methods, counseling, and organizational competencies should be prioritized in teacher education programs. Schools must also have ample resources like assistive technology and teaching materials, and other adaptations that will allow catering to various students. Results of this study demonstrate a need for a joint action among educators, policymakers, and school administrators toward school climate change. Classroom diversity can be prepared through evaluations and feedback by teachers at proper intervals. Furthermore, there is a place to improve the environment of empathy and

continuous learning among educators through promoting the intellectual, social, and emotional development of kids with special needs.

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